

BUILDING THE FOUNDATION: HOW LITERACY AND NUMERACY SKILLS IN THIRD GRADE IMPACT OVERALL ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the factors influencing academic performance in Grade 3 students within the District of Motiong, Schools Division of Samar (School Year 2023-2024). The research aimed to understand how literacy and numeracy program implementation impacted student achievement. Findings revealed a high level of program integration into curriculum and teaching practices. However, high implementation alone did not guarantee improved performance. Age differences emerged, with older students showing stronger engagement in numeracy but potentially struggling with fluency. Gender did not significantly impact perceived literacy program effectiveness, suggesting equitable instruction. Socioeconomic factors played a role, with students from higher-income families having access to resources that enhanced numeracy engagement. Similarly, access to reading materials at home influenced literacy development. Positive attitudes and parental education were linked to effective program implementation in both literacy and numeracy. Furthermore, the study found strong connections between effective instruction and student academic performance. While the overall system supported learning, a small percentage of students scored below the benchmark, highlighting the need for targeted interventions. The research identified key factors for academic success: differentiated instruction, addressing gender disparities, supporting students from diverse backgrounds, providing resources, fostering positive attitudes, and parental involvement. Recommendations include: implementing differentiated instruction, investigating gender differences, providing interventions for students facing socioeconomic challenges, promoting resource access, fostering positive attitudes, encouraging parental engagement, and implementing evidence-based literacy and numeracy programs with effective teaching strategies. By

creating supportive learning environments, educators can equip all students to reach their full potential.

Keywords: *Grade 3 Students, Academic Performance, Literacy Programs, Numeracy Programs, Program Implementation, Differentiated Instruction, Socioeconomic Status, Parental Involvement, Positive Attitudes, Reading Fluency, Targeted Interventions, Learning Environment, Effective Teaching Strategies, Student Engagement*

INTRODUCTION

The Department of Education has long been concerned with numeracy and literacy, recognizing their importance as fundamental skills. Efforts and mechanisms have consistently been prioritized and implemented by the department to bridge gaps in numeracy and literacy education. This commitment reflects the department's dedication to delivering quality and relevant education to learners, acknowledging that numeracy and literacy form the foundation for academic success and lifelong learning. Proficiency in numeracy equips students with essential mathematical abilities, enabling them to solve problems, make informed decisions, and navigate the complexities of daily life. Similarly, literacy skills empower students to comprehend, communicate, and critically analyze information across various disciplines.

Academic performance encompasses a student's achievements, progress, and competence in various educational domains. It serves as a crucial indicator of a student's learning outcomes, educational attainment, and overall success in formal education. It is influenced by multiple factors, including student motivation, engagement, study habits, instructional quality, school environment, and support systems (Caprara, et al., 2000). Monitoring and fostering positive academic performance are essential for educators, institutions, and policymakers, as it not only reflects the effectiveness of educational systems but also play a significant role in shaping students' future opportunities and prospects (Singh & Shaari, 2019). By identifying and addressing the factors contributing to academic performance, educators can provide targeted interventions and support systems to enhance student learning outcomes and ensure educational success.

A nation's greatness is characterized by its literate society, high civilization, and active contributions to the world society. Literacy goes beyond mere eradication of illiteracy; it encompasses the ability of citizens to compete and coexist globally. A nation with a strong literacy culture demonstrates its communicative, creative, critical thinking, and collaborative abilities, enabling it to excel in global competition (Majorano et al., 2021).

In the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 and Society 5.0, education must be based on 21st-century skills, including literacy, competence, and character. Six fundamental

literacies shape students' development of these skills: literacy, numeracy literacy, science literacy, financial literacy, digital literacy, cultural literacy, and citizenship (Castner et al., 2020).

The Philippines faces a significant challenge with a high rate of low performers among PISA-participating countries and economies. The 2018 PISA report revealed that 71.8 percent of participating students from the Philippines have failed to reach minimum basic learning thresholds, raising doubts about the state of education in the country (Alinsunurin, 2021). Their poor scores in English, Mathematics, and Science can be attributed to a lack of basic reading and comprehension abilities. A World Bank report from last year revealed that Filipino students scored poorly on math, science, and literacy assessments, compounded by issues like bullying and health problems such as malnutrition.

To address these challenges, the Department of Education (DepEd) launched the "Hamon: Bawat Bata Bumabasa" (3Bs Initiatives) as explicitly stated in DepEd Memorandum Number 173 Series of 2019. This initiative aims to intensify the advocacy for reading and commits to making every learner a reader at their grade level. Early exposure to Mathematics is also recognized as a factor that increases students' odds of achieving academic and personal success in school and life. Additionally, early reading instruction is considered one of the most crucial outcomes of primary education, as it develops comprehensive literacy skills necessary for successful participation in society. The interplay between numeracy and literacy is integral to the learning process of students. The language of Mathematics involves creating and communicating mathematical meanings using context-appropriate language, which goes beyond recognizing and responding to isolated words (Domingo, 2021). This requires the use of words and symbols that match the cognitive abilities of the learners involved. Communicating mathematical concepts effectively is challenging, especially when the teacher and student have different preferred languages (Janes & Strong, 2014).

Literacy and numeracy skills are fundamental components of a child's education, playing a crucial role in their academic development and future success (Souviney, 2013). Grade 3 is a critical stage in a student's educational journey, marking the transition from foundational learning to more advanced subject areas. Understanding the factors influencing the academic performance of Grade 3 students, particularly in terms of literacy and numeracy, is essential for designing effective educational interventions and improving overall learning outcomes.

Previous studies have shown that a student's English proficiency influences their performance in Mathematics. There is a strong correlation between English reading and measures of cognitive development and mathematical accomplishments (Sindoni et al., 2021). Language in Mathematics instruction serves to facilitate precise communication of mathematical knowledge between instructors and students. Using a language that matches the cognitive abilities of students in terms of structure, meaning, technical vocabulary, and symbolism is vital for achieving the goals of Mathematics education. However, the interpretation of messages can be subjective, highlighting the importance

of clear communication (Slusser, 2019).

The impact of this situation is starkly reflected in the literacy and numeracy assessment performance of Grade 3 students in the Motiong District. According to the consolidated data from the Philippine Reading Inventory for Grade 3 learners, the figures are concerning. In the academic years 2020-2021, 2021-2022, and 2022-2023, out of 287, 268, and 274 students respectively, a significant portion, approximately 31% in each year, were classified as being at the frustration level, as reported by District PROMEDS. Similarly, when examining the numeracy levels within the same cohort, the results are equally troubling. In the years 2020-2021, 2021-2022, and 2022-2023, out of 287, 268, and 274 students respectively, a concerning percentage, ranging from 31% to 35%, were identified as non-numerates according to District PROMEDS. These findings underscore a pressing need for targeted interventions and educational strategies to address the literacy and numeracy challenges faced by Grade 3 students in Motiong District.

While existing research has emphasized the importance of literacy and numeracy skills for academic achievement, there is still a gap in understanding the specific factors influencing the performance of Grade 3 students. Most studies have focused on the general relationship between literacy/numeracy and academic achievement without considering the nuances within the Grade 3 context. This study aims to address this research gap by investigating the unique challenges and opportunities Grade 3 students face in developing their literacy and numeracy skills and how these skills impact their academic performance. The findings will provide insights to inform educational policies and practices that promote better learning outcomes for Grade 3 students.

Furthermore, examining the interaction between literacy and numeracy skills can uncover potential synergistic effects when these skills are taught in an integrated manner. Considering the intertwined nature of literacy and numeracy, educators can develop instructional strategies that facilitate cross-domain learning, leading to enhanced academic outcomes for Grade 3 students. While existing research has explored the impacts of literacy and numeracy skills on academic performance, there is a need for more studies focusing specifically on the joint effect of these skills within the Grade 3 context. Addressing this research gap will provide valuable insights for educators and policymakers, enabling them to comprehensively develop Grade 3 students and make informed decisions to optimize their academic achievement.

Research Questions

This study delved into determining the effect of literacy and numeracy on the academic performance of Grade 3 students in the District of Motiong, Schools Division of Samar during the School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the Grade 3 students in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 age and sex;
 - 1.2. parents' highest educational attainment;

- 1.3. gross monthly family income;
 - 1.4 parents' occupation;
 - 1.5 final grade in English and Mathematics in the previous grade level;
 - 1.6 reading materials utilized at home;
 - 1.7 numeracy materials utilized at home; and
 - 1.8 attitude toward numeracy and literacy?
2. What is the level of implementation of numeracy program in the District of Motiong as assessed by the student respondents in terms of the following:
- 2.1 activities and strategies;
 - 2.2 Mathematics assessment;
 - 2.3 class structures;
 - 2.4 student engagement;
 - 2.5 learning environment/materials; and
 - 2.6 principles on Mathematics instruction?
3. What is the level of implementation of literacy program in the District of Motiong as assessed by the student respondents in terms of the following:
- 3.1 reading components and early literacy strategies;
 - 3.2 decoding and word analysis;
 - 3.3 phonological awareness;
 - 3.4 vocabulary in context;
 - 3.5 fluency;
 - 3.6 class structures;
 - 3.7 student engagement;
 - 3.8 learning environment/materials;
 - 3.9 reading principles of literacy instruction; and
 - 3.10 reading assessment?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the students' personal profile and the following:
- 4.1 numeracy program implementation; and
 - 4.2 literacy program implementation?
5. What is the academic performance of the student-respondents based on the first and second quarters during the School Year 2023-2024?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance of the Grade 3 student-respondents and the following:
- 6.1 student-related variates;
 - 6.2 perceived level of numeracy program implementation; and
 - 6.3 perceived level of literacy program implementation?
7. What are the problems encountered by student-respondents with regard to numeracy and literacy program implementation?

Locale of the Study

Figure 1
The Map Showing the Locale of the Study

Figure 1 displays the vicinity map of Motiong, Samar. The study would be conducted in the District of Motiong, which is located in the Division of Samar. Motiong is classified as a fourth-class municipality and is one of the towns within Samar Province. The District of Motiong comprises twenty-nine (29) elementary schools.

METHODOLOGY

This research used a quantitative approach to explore the connection between how well literacy and numeracy programs are implemented and how well Grade 3 students perform academically. The study focused on 181 Grade 3 students in the District of Motiong. A questionnaire was the main tool for collecting data. This questionnaire was adopted from the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development's (2015) publication titled "Teacher Education Program on Early Numeracy and Literacy". The parts of the questionnaire that asked about students themselves were reviewed by a panel of experts to make sure they were accurate and appropriate. To collect the data, the researcher got permission from various school officials and then personally conducted the survey. The surveys were done one-on-one in a private location to protect the students' privacy. Finally, after all the data was collected, it was analyzed using statistical methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following were the salient findings of the study:

1. Most of the students are between 8 and 9 years old; had a relatively balanced sex distribution, parents reached Elementary Graduate within the PHP5,001-10,000 income bracket, most fathers were self-employed while the majority of mothers were unemployed. Moreover, most students performed well in both subjects (Scores 90-100 in English & Mathematics, the most used reading material are books and dictionaries. They usually used money, clock, and counting objects used at home, and had an uncertain attitude towards numeracy and literacy.
2. Generally, the level of numeracy program implementation was highly evident. In particular, class structures (mean =4.17), student engagement (mean=4.14), learning environment (mean=4.06), mathematics assessment (mean=3.84), and activities and strategies (mean=3.77).
3. The level of implementation of the literacy program was Highly Evident along reading components and early literacy strategies (mean=4.27), decoding and word analysis (mean=3.64), phonological awareness (mean=3.84), vocabulary in context (mean=4.26), fluency(mean=4.47), class structures (mean=4.22), student engagement (mean=3.84), learning environment/materials, reading principles of literacy instruction (mean=4.39), and reading assessment (mean=4.12).
4. The student's age and the perceived level of implementation of numeracy program along with student engagement was significantly correlated with their age ($r=0.204$, $p=0.006$). While, student's perceived level of literacy program implementation along fluency ($r=-0.165$, $p=0.027$) and reading assessment

($r=0.147$, $p=0.048$) were significantly correlated with their age.

5. Along with the level of numeracy program Implementation, the sex category of the student respondents had a significant relationship with their perceived level of numeracy program implementation along activities and strategies ($r=-0.178$, $p=0.016$). Along with literacy program implementation, the sex category of the student-respondents had no significant relationship with their perceived level of literacy program implementation ($p>0.05$).
6. In terms of numeracy program implementation, the gross family monthly income of the student-respondents had a significant relationship with their perceived level of numeracy program implementation along with the following domains: activities and strategies ($r=0.331$, $p<0.001$); mathematics assessment ($r=0.249$, $p=0.001$); student engagement in numeracy programs ($r=0.237$, $p=0.001$), and principles of mathematics instruction ($r=0.274$, $p<0.001$). On the other hand, along with literacy program implementation, the gross family monthly income of the student-respondents had a significant relationship with their perceived level of literacy program implementation along with the following domains: reading components and early literacy strategies ($r=0.382$, $p<0.001$); decoding and word analysis ($r=0.363$, $p<0.001$); vocabulary in context ($r=0.381$, $p<0.001$), and reading assessment ($r=0.418$, $p<0.001$).
7. In terms of the numeracy program implementation, the reading materials utilized at home by the students had no significant correlation with their perceived level of numeracy program implementation ($p>0.05$). Meanwhile, in the literacy program implementation, the reading materials utilized at home by the students had a significant correlation with their perceived level of implementation along the following domains: phonological awareness ($r=0.189$, $p=0.011$); fluency ($r=-0.154$, $p=0.039$); student engagement ($r=0.189$, $p=0.011$), and learning environment/materials ($r=0.171$, $p=0.022$).
8. Along with the numeracy program implementation, the number of numeracy materials utilized at home was significantly related to the program implementation along activities and strategies ($r=0.189$, $p=0.011$) and student engagement ($r=0.215$, $p=0.004$); However, along with the literacy program implementation, the number of numeracy materials utilized at home had a significant relationship with the following domain of implementation: Decoding and word analysis ($r=0.199$, $p<0.05$); Phonological awareness ($r=0.158$, $p<0.05$); Vocabulary in context ($r=0.163$, $p<0.05$); fluency ($r=-0.228$, $p<0.05$); Reading principles of literacy instruction ($r=0.186$, $p<0.05$), and Reading assessment ($r=0.297$, $p<0.05$).
9. Along with the numeracy program implementation, the student's attitude towards numeracy and literacy shows a significant association with the following domains of implementation: activities and strategies ($r=0.781$, $p<0.001$); student engagement ($r=0.492$, $p<0.001$); learning

- environment/materials ($r=0.346$, $p<0.001$), and principles on mathematics instruction ($r=0.460$, $p<0.001$). While, in terms of literacy program implementation, the student's attitude towards numeracy and literacy shows a significant association with the following domains of implementation: reading components and early literacy strategies ($r=0.229$, $p=0.002$); decoding, phonological awareness, vocabulary in context, and fluency ($p<0.05$); student engagement, learning environment/materials, reading principles of literacy instruction, reading assessment ($p<0.05$).
10. Along with the numeracy program implementation, the parent's educational attainment shows a significant association with the following domain of implementation: activities and strategies (both parents, $p<0.05$); mathematics assessment (father, $p<0.05$); class structure (mother, $p<0.05$); student engagement (both parents, $p<0.05$); Learning environment/materials (both parents, $p<0.05$), and principles on Mathematics instruction (both parents, $p<0.05$). While, in terms with the literacy program implementation, the parent's educational attainment shows a significant association with the following domain of implementation: Reading components and early literacy strategies (both parents, $p<0.05$); Decoding and word analysis (both parents, $p<0.05$); Phonological awareness (both parents, $p<0.05$); Vocabulary in context (both parents, $p<0.05$); Fluency (mother, $p<0.05$); Student engagement (mother, $p<0.05$); Learning environment/materials (mother, $p<0.05$); Reading principles of literacy instruction (both parents, $p<0.05$); Reading assessment (both parents, $p<0.05$).
 11. In terms of the numeracy program implementation, the student's final grade in Math and English shows a significant association with all the domains of the program implementation except with the mathematics assessment ($p>0.05$). In terms of the literacy program implementation, the student's final grade in Math and English shows a significant association with all the domains of the program implementation except for the class structures ($p>0.05$).
 12. The students in Motiong District achieved high academic performance, with 23.2% scoring between 90-100 and 28.2% scoring between 80-84.
 13. The academic performance was significantly related with the following student's profile: age ($r = -.159$, $p = .033$) ; gross family monthly income ($r = .256$, $p<0.05$); parent's educational attainment ($p<0.05$); number of numeracy materials utilized at home and attitudes towards numeracy and literacy ($p<0.05$), and students' final grades in English and Math and their overall academic performance ($r = .620$, $p = .000$ for English; $r = .682$, $p = .000$ for Math).
 14. Along with numeracy and literacy program implementation, the student's academic performance had a significant correlation between their perceived level of numeracy and literacy program implementation except for the

implementation of mathematics assessment ($p>0.05$).

15. The students found three indicators that they considered as Highly a Problem were the following: lack of time management (mean=3.56); lack of drill work (3.54), and grasping concepts slowly (mean=3.35).

Attitude toward Numeracy and Literacy of the Student-Respondents

Table 1 shows the attitude toward numeracy and literacy of the student-respondents.

Table 1

Attitude toward Numeracy and Literacy of the Student-Respondents

	Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1.	I really like Mathematics and English.	3.51	1.75	Agree
2.	I am happy in my Mathematics and English classes compared to other classes.	3.39	1.7	Undecided
3.	I think studying advanced Mathematics and English is useful.	4.64	0.75	Strongly Agree
4.	Mathematics and English are very interesting to me.	3.40	1.66	Uncertain
5.	I believe studying Mathematics and English helps me with problem-solving in other subjects.	4.61	0.82	Strongly Agree
6.	I am comfortable answering Math problems and indulge in selection reading in class.	3.30	1.65	Uncertain
7.	I have a lot of self-confidence when it comes to Mathematics and English.	3.35	1.74	Uncertain
8.	I am always under terrible strain in Math and English class.	2.64	1.51	Uncertain
9.	Studying Mathematics and English makes me feel nervous/uneasy.	2.60	1.52	Uncertain
10.	Mathematics and English make me feel irritable.	2.60	1.42	Uncertain
Grand Weighted Mean		3.40		Uncertain

Legend:

- 4.50-5.00 Strongly Agree
- 3.50-4.49 Agree
- 2.50-3.49 Uncertain/Undecided
- 1.50-2.49 Disagree
- 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree

The results revealed that students have an overall uncertain attitude towards numeracy and literacy, with a grand mean of 3.40. Some of the key findings were as follows: Students agree that they like Mathematics and English (mean=3.51) and are undecided about being happier in these classes compared to others (mean=3.39); they were also uncertain about Mathematics and English for being interesting to them (mean=3.40), being comfortable answering math problems and doing reading in class (mean=3.30), and having self-confidence in these subjects (mean=3.35). Much that they were uncertain about feeling terrible strain (mean=2.64), nervous/uneasy (mean=2.60), and irritable (mean=2.60) when studying Mathematics and English.

On the other hands, students strongly agree that studying advanced Mathematics and English is useful (mean=4.64) and that it helps them with problem-solving in other subjects (mean=4.61).

These results suggest that while students recognize the usefulness and importance of numeracy and literacy skills, they may lack confidence, interest, and comfort in these areas. This could be due to various factors such as teaching methods, learning resources, or prior experiences.

Conclusions

From the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The demographic profile of Grade 3 students in Motiong District suggests that most students are performing well academically, with a significant portion scoring in the 90-100 range in both English and Math. However, the relatively balanced sex distribution, parents' educational attainment, and family income levels indicate that socioeconomic factors may not be the primary drivers of academic success in this population. The use of common household items for numeracy practice and the uncertain attitude towards literacy and numeracy among students could be areas for further investigation and potential intervention
2. The high level of implementation of the numeracy program in Grade 3 classrooms in Motiong District, particularly in areas such as class structures, student engagement, learning environment, mathematics assessment, and activities and strategies, suggests that these factors contribute positively to students' numeracy skills development. However, high implementation levels alone do not guarantee improved academic performance, and other factors, such as the quality of instruction and student motivation.
3. The highly evident implementation of the literacy program in Grade 3 classrooms in Motiong District, particularly in areas such as reading components and early literacy strategies, decoding and word analysis, phonological awareness, vocabulary in context, fluency, class structures, student engagement, learning environment/materials, reading principles of literacy instruction, and reading

assessment, indicates that these factors are well-integrated into the curriculum and teaching practices. This comprehensive approach to literacy instruction likely contributes to the overall academic performance of students in the district. However, it is essential to continuously monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of these practices to ensure that they are meeting the diverse needs of all students.

4. The older students tend to be more engaged in numeracy activities compared to younger students. However, older students may struggle with fluency but perform better on reading assessments.
5. Gender differences in how students engage with and respond to certain numeracy activities and teaching strategies may be considered. However, the lack of a significant relationship between sex and perceived literacy program implementation implies that literacy instruction may be more equitable across genders.
6. Students from higher-income families may have access to more resources and support that enhance their engagement and performance in numeracy programs. Similarly, socioeconomic status may play a role in literacy development.
7. Access to reading materials at home can enhance certain aspects of literacy development. However, reading materials alone may not be sufficient to improve fluency.
8. Access to numeracy materials can enhance engagement and participation in numeracy-related activities. Similarly, numeracy materials can also support certain aspects of literacy development. However, numeracy materials alone may not be sufficient to improve fluency.
9. A positive attitude can enhance engagement and performance in numeracy programs. Similarly, a positive attitude can also support various aspects of literacy development.
10. Higher parental education levels are associated with more effective implementation of numeracy programs. Similarly, parental education plays a role in the effectiveness of literacy instruction.
11. Effective numeracy instruction is closely linked to academic performance. Similarly, high-quality literacy instruction is also associated with academic success.
12. Educational system in the district is effectively supporting student learning and achievement. However, it is important to note that a small percentage of students (2.8%) scored below 75, indicating the need for targeted interventions and support to ensure that all students have the opportunity to succeed academically.
13. Older students may face challenges in keeping up with their grade level. socioeconomic status can be a barrier to academic success. parental involvement and support in student learning. access to resources, positive attitudes, and strong

foundational skills in core subjects are key factors in academic achievement.

14. Effective instructional practices in these areas are closely linked to academic success. However, assessment practices may not be as strongly associated with performance as other aspects of numeracy and literacy instruction.
15. The top three problems provide valuable insights into areas where additional support and interventions may be needed.

Recommendations

Anchored on the conclusions drawn from the findings, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Differentiated instruction and targeted support to address students' varying literacy and numeracy needs at different ages may be introduced.
2. Further investigation may be conducted to understand the underlying factors contributing to gender differences and ensure that all students, regardless of sex, have equal opportunities to develop their numeracy skills.
3. Interventions and support may be imposed to ensure that students from all socioeconomic backgrounds have equal opportunities to succeed academically.
4. Variety of numeracy and literacy resources and support both at home and in the classroom may be recommended to foster comprehensive skills.
5. Targeted interventions may be recommended for fostering positive attitudes towards numeracy and literacy through engaging instructional practices, supportive learning environments, to help students achieve academic success.
6. Parents may encourage to engage in their children's education and provide support to families to enhance student learning outcomes.
7. Evidence-based, comprehensive numeracy and literacy programs that prioritize effective teaching strategies, learning environments, and student engagement to support academic achievement may be implemented.
8. Educators may create more supportive and effective learning environments that enable students to reach their full potential.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study prioritized ethical research practices. Students participating in the survey were thoroughly informed about the research goals, both through written materials and verbal explanations. They were also assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any point, without needing to give a reason. Additionally, strong

measures were put in place to safeguard the confidentiality of all student information.

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